

Gothic Cathedrals and Scholasticism

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Abstract

This article examines the development of Gothic cathedral architecture in Western Europe from the twelfth to the fifteenth centuries, with particular attention to the architectural transformation from Romanesque mass and enclosure to Gothic height, luminosity, and structural articulation. It explains the importance of the pointed arch, ribbed vault, and flying buttress as technical solutions that made possible taller buildings, larger interior spaces, thinner walls, and expansive stained-glass windows. Beginning with the Abbey Church of St. Denis and the work of Abbot Suger, the article traces the spread of Gothic architecture across Europe and places its structural innovations within a longer historical development reaching back through Romanesque, Roman, Byzantine, Islamic, and ancient architectural forms.

The article also considers Gothic cathedrals as expressions of medieval intellectual and spiritual life. Drawing on the connection between Gothic architecture and Scholasticism, it presents the cathedral not simply as a building, but as a synthesis of matter and form, faith and reason, theology and logic, craftsmanship and metaphysics. The same impulse toward order, clarity, totality, and manifestation that shaped the Scholastic *summa* also appears in the Gothic cathedral, where visible structure, symbolic space, and religious purpose are joined in stone, glass, and light.

A further purpose of the article is to recover the voice and authority of older works of architectural, historical, and philosophical scholarship. By engaging substantial texts by writers such as Porter, O'Reilly, Moore, Lethaby, Pevsner, Panofsky, Maritain, and De Wulf, the article presents Gothic architecture through books of lasting scholarly and literary quality. In this sense, the article is both a historical study of Gothic cathedrals and Scholastic thought, and an invitation to encounter the older tradition of serious writing about art, architecture, religion, and civilization.

The term “Gothic architecture” refers to an architectural style in Western Europe from about the middle of twelfth century to the end of fifteenth century. It is generally considered that Gothic architecture began in the region of France around Paris. Abbey Church of St. Denis, which began to be rebuilt in the new style around 1140 and was finished and dedicated on June 11, 1144, is considered to be the first Gothic cathedral.

Gothic style spread throughout Europe with dozens of Gothic cathedrals built or remodeled in the new style. Examples include St. Denis (1144), Notre Dame de Paris (1160), Reims (1211), Amiens (1220) in France; Canterbury (1174), York Minster (1220), Salisbury (1220) in England; Magdeburg (1209), Cologne (1248), Regensburg (1280) in Germany; León (1205), Burgos (1221), Toledo (1226) in Spain; Martin's Church (1225), Antwerp (1352) in Netherlands; St. Paul in Liège (1275), St. Bavo (1274) in Belgium; St. John in Wrocław (1272), and Sandomierz (1360) in Poland; St. Wenceslas (1265), Assumption of Our Lady (1300), St. Vitus (1344) in Czech Republic; Matthias Church (1255) in Hungary; Riga Cathedral (1211) in Latvia; St. Nicholas Church (1385) in Lithuania.

In Italy, Gothic style was never fully accepted. Italian Gothic churches always retained the elements of Romanesque (Frothingham, 1891). Examples of Italian Gothic cathedrals include Chiaravalle Abbey and Milan Cathedral in Milan; Basilica di Sant'Andrea in Vercelli; Basilica of San Francesco of Assisi in Assisi; and Santa Maria Novella in Florence. The fifteenth century is considered by historians to be the time of a decline in Gothic style and transition to Baroque. (Bialostocki, 1966; Cullen, 2000)

The main features of Gothic architectural style are pointed arch, flying buttress, and rib vault. These architectural elements greatly strengthened the framework of the construction enabling a much higher building height. Buttresses, by taking the weight of the roof off the walls, allowed for very large and tall clerestory windows with very elaborate stained-glass work that lighted the whole interior of the cathedral. High pointed arches and ribbed vaults allowed for efficient distribution of an enormous weight of the vault and, by greatly strengthening building's framework, enabled construction of very tall churches with huge interior spaces that were not seen in earlier Romanesque churches. Earlier churches used so-called tunnel and groin vaults to construct ceilings. Tunnel vault presses down on whole length of walls, requiring very thick walls. The main weight of Romanesque groin vaults pressed down on the four corners, requiring square bays for stability and

semicircular arches to support the roof. This point is succinctly stated by Fred Crossley writing in England during World War II:

From the twelfth century onwards architecture had continuous development, especially in the scientific use of materials. There was a consistent striving to improve construction and minimize the weight of material. These efforts were principally directed towards solving the difficult problems of throwing a vault of stone over an uneven space keeping at the same time an even keel. The solution was eventually found in the pointed arch, and, from its use as constructional expedience, it was later developed as a decorative feature, becoming the main factor in what is called “Gothic architecture”. (Crossley, 1941, p. 3)

The same emphasis on the importance of finding effective structural solutions for the construction of large stone structures is elegantly expressed by Elizabeth O’Reilly:

The thrust of a barrel vault was exerted along the whole length of the wall, which necessitated a continuous abutment – an enormously thick wall. Only small windows could be opened. Since Romanesque architect had the ambition to light his church well, and not to encumber his floor surface by clumsy piers, a barrel vaulting could be but a temporary solution of the main problem...When, under some groin vault, some obscure mason constructed the earliest intersecting stone ribs, the first step in Gothic architecture had been taken...The force of expansion was counteracted by a proportionate force of compression. By means of a framework made up of vault ribs, of piers, of buttresses, and flying buttresses, the edifice became a living skeleton. The walls between the active members, when relieved of their load, served merely as screen enclosures and could be carved into fragile beauty and hung with transparent tapestries of colored glass. Because the flying buttress transmitted a large part of the vault’s pressure to the exterior buttress piles, the piers within the church could be lessened in diameter, and greater capacity be given to the interior. (O’Reilly, 1921, p. 25)

Pointed arch, ribbed vault, and flying buttress are humble architectural constructs, but their importance in architectural history cannot be overstated. These devices

have provided architectural solutions that enabled a new era in the history of human development which produced unequalled masterpieces of Medieval Gothic cathedrals. It bears repeating that the pointed arch enabled much greater building height than semicircular arch because pointed arch produces more vertical downward thrust, which is structurally much safer than a more horizontal thrust made by a semicircular arch. The pointed arch enabled construction of long rectangular bays where the weight of roof and the upper part of the building was distributed over longer walls supported by flying buttresses. Longer, taller bays created huge interior spaces characteristic of Gothic cathedrals.

The pointed arch, flying buttress, and rib vault, however, are not inventions of the twelfth century, but the development of Romanesque architectural style. Romanesque style itself was an organic development of architectural styles and techniques from preceding eras. Pointed arch is a development of a semicircular arch that was already known in Ancient Mesopotamia. Famous example of very large brick vault is the arch of Taq-i Kisra in the ruins of Ctesiphon in Iraq, built in 3rd century A.D. Semicircular arches have been widely used throughout the North Africa, Middle East, and Roman Empire. Notable example is Palace of Ardashir Pāpakan in Iran (built circ. 225 A.D.) with three domes, massive walls and round arches, Great Mosque of Kairouan, Tunisia (built circ. 670 A.D.) with innumerable “horseshoe” arches throughout great prayer hall supported by hundreds of columns. The walls of the enclosure of the Great Mosque have massive wall buttresses along the whole perimeter. Another example is Samanid Mausoleum in Bukhara, Uzbekistan (built 842-943 A.D.) with an ingenious system of semicircular arches supporting hemispherical dome on an octagonal base that rests on four walls. (Hoag, 1963)

The barrel vault was used widely throughout Roman Empire. The groin vault (cross vault) is essentially two intersecting barrel vaults. Such vaulting has a long history predating Middle Ages. For example, the great rectangular hall of Basilica of Maxentius and Constantine (built 308-312 A.D.) in the Roman Forum is roofed by cross (groin) vaults supported by columns 18 meters high. Other outstanding examples of the use of groin vaults and semicircular arches in Rome are Baths of Caracalla (built 212-216 AD) and the Baths of Diocletian (built 298-306 AD). (Bailey, 1921; Roth, 1993)

A wall buttress (abutment, counterfort) which is used to support and reinforce walls, must be one of the oldest architectural elements used in all parts of the world

since antiquity. Famous early examples of wall buttresses in large structures are Mesopotamian ziggurats, such as Ziggurat of Ur in Iraq, built over 4000 years ago in 21st century BC. An outstanding modern example of using buttresses in the construction of very large structures is Burj Khalifa in Dubai (completed in 2009), standing at 828 meters high.

One of the main elements of Gothic architecture, flying buttress, is a technological development of an ordinary buttress types, such angled, clasping, or diagonal “French” buttresses. Outstanding examples of the use of ordinary wall buttresses, as opposed to flying buttresses, are presented by many Romanesque churches, such as St. Marie-Madeleine in Vezelay, St. Martin in Chapaize, Abbey Church of The Holy Trinity in Caen, France; Holy Trinity in Blythburgh, Beverley Minster in Beverley, Dunfermline Abbey in Dunfermline, UK. Gradually, ordinary buttress used in Romanesque churches was transformed into a “flying buttresses” to meet new architectural demands. Large, complex extended flying buttresses became a characteristic feature of Gothic cathedrals. Flying buttresses, however, were used for wall support long before they were universally employed in the construction of Gothic cathedrals. For example, the austere and sublime Basilica of St. Vitale in Ravenna (built 526-547 A.D.) has massive extended flying buttresses. The Basilica is built with Roman and Byzantine architectural elements whose roots go far into the past. (Porter, 1909; Bailey, 1921)

The Roman style of building, which developed into Romanesque style over the centuries, was based on ancient basilica. An arched (barrel) roof was put on two walls. The walls had to be thick in order to withstand the weight of the roof and upper part of the building. The arched or vaulted roof generates side thrust that would buckle and crumble walls, unless walls were sufficiently thick or supported by buttresses (counterforts). The larger and taller structures with heavier roofs required very sturdy, thick walls. The architects, the medieval masons, began to use pointed arches and ribbed groin vaults to strengthen the construction. They supported such architectural *ensemble* by means of flying buttresses rather than by heavy walls. The system of pointed arches, ribbed groin vaults, and flying buttresses constituted the frame-work of a building. It is this unique frame-work that distinguishes Gothic from Romanesque epoch. In the words of Charles Moore:

A system which was a gradual evolution out of Romanesque; and one whose distinctive characteristic is that the whole character of the

building is determined by, and its whole strength is made to reside in, a finely organized and frankly confessed, frame-work, rather than walls. (Moore, 1904, p. 8)

In the words of one of the foremost experts on Medieval architecture, Arthur Kingsley Porter, whose truly seminal work “Medieval Architecture” is in high demand by scholars and professional architects even today, 110 years after publication:

The greatest of all the marvels of the Gothic cathedral is the age which produced it. Amid the broils of robber-barons, amid the clamor of communes and contending factions, amid the ignorance and superstition of the Church, this lovely art, at once so intellectual and so ideal, suddenly burst into flower. It seems almost like an anachronism, that this architecture should have arisen in the turbulent Middle Ages. Yet Gothic architecture, although in a sense so distinctly opposed to the spirit of the times, was none the less deeply imbued with that spirit of the times, and can be understood only when considered in relation to contemporary political, ecclesiastical, economic, and social conditions. (Porter, 1909, p. 145)

The transition from Romanesque to Gothic is not only a succession between two architectural styles, however significant. This transition is a paradigmatic change in the ever-developing human history. It affected architecture, sculpture, and eventually painting. One of the principal causes of this change, besides purely architectural and technical innovations, is the rise of scholasticism. Eminent scholar of the medieval period, Erwin Panofsky, argued this point with close attention to architecture:

High Scholastic philosophy, however, severely limited the sanctuary of faith from the sphere of rational knowledge yet insisted that the content of this sanctuary remain clearly discernible. And so did High Gothic architecture delimit interior volume from exterior space yet insist that it protect itself, as it were, through the encompassing structure; so that, for example, the cross section of the nave can be read off from the facade. Like High Scholastic, the High Gothic cathedral aimed, first of all, at ‘totality’ and therefore tended to approximate, by synthesis as well as elimination, one perfect and final solution. In its imagery, the High Gothic cathedral sought to embody the whole of Christian knowledge, theological, moral, natural, and

historical, with everything in its place and that which no longer found its place, suppressed. (Panofsky, 1957, p. 44)

W. H. Goodyear, in his “Roman and Medieval Art”, writes that Gothic style is known in France as “flamboyant” or “flaming”. The Gothic architectural style was also known during the medieval period as “*Opus Francigenum*”, *i.e.*, “French work”. Artists and critics of Italian Renaissance (14th to 16th centuries) held a negative view of the medieval period, which they contrasted with Classical age of Greece and Rome. They criticized Gothic architecture as ugly and devoid of artistic qualities. The word “Gothic” was adopted from the name of people (Visigoths) who sacked Rome in 410 A.D. Visigoths was a branch of Germanic tribes known to Romans as “Goths”. Giorgio Vasari, eminent Italian writer and art critic of sixteenth century, called Gothic art and architecture “monstrous and barbarous” (1530). This slur was later adopted by the Neo-Classicists of seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. In France, Racine called Gothic art “barbarous”, Voltaire called it “coarse curiosity lacking in good taste”, Moliere said that Gothic “waged a mortal battle with refinement” and Gothic cathedrals were “monsters of ignorant times”. In late eighteenth century, during French revolution, all symbols of French Monarchy including religion were attacked. It was proposed to free France from Gothic cathedrals, these “overcharged facades, with their multitudes of indecent and ridiculous figures”. (Goodyear, 1893; Kingsley 1899; O’Reilly, 1921)

Throughout France, many cathedrals were destroyed or defaced, such as churches of St. Marital in Limoges and St. Benigne at Dijon, the abbey at Jumieges, Cluny abbey near Macon, basilica of S. Martin in Tours, and countless others. Later, during Gothic Revival of nineteenth century, Gothic cathedrals were recognized as magnificent architectural and artistic creations that represented, besides new architectural ideas and technics, the synthesis of spiritual and temporal, religious faith with philosophy and logic, created in stone with immense effort and skill.

William Lethaby, British historian and the Surveyor of Westminster Abbey in the beginning of twentieth century, writes movingly about the inseparability of Gothic architecture and the epoch in which it was made:

This art was the expression of Folk mind; the spirit and body were inseparable. The difference between modern “design in Gothic style” and the real thing is that one is a whim of fashion, the other was a function of life. (Lethaby, 1926, p. 60)

The same point about the essential unity between the art and the society in which it is created, is made by Jacques Maritain, one of the greatest Catholic philosophers of 20th century:

Religious art is not a thing which can be isolated from the general artistic movement of an age. The art of a period carries with it all the intellectual and spiritual stuff which constitutes the life of the period. (Maritain, 1943, p. 142)

In theology and philosophy, medieval scholastics believed in an Aristotelian view of unity between the essence and form. Scholastics used two Aristotelian doctrines: first, the immanent form enters into the actual composition with matter; second, the rational soul is the substantial form of the body. Man is a unified being – we can speak of man as a personified soul or a spiritualized body. This is scholastic hylomorphism which is a metaphysical position that had great influence on all aspects of medieval life, including architecture. (Powicke, 1926; Maritain, 1943; Cullen, 2000)

Gothic style was much more than simply new, effective architectural methods and principles of building. As Erwin Panofsky expressed it with his usual elegance and *manière savante*:

A man imbued with the Scholastic habit would look upon the mode of architectural presentation, just as he looked upon the mode of literacy presentation, from the point of view of *manifestation* (which means "evident, plain, palpable"). He would have taken it for granted that the primary purpose of the many elements that compose a cathedral was to ensure stability, just as he took it for granted that the primary purpose of many elements that constitute a *Summa* was to ensure validity. (Panofsky, 1957, p. 58)

The concept of synthesis was very common in medieval thought as evidenced by many Scholastic *summa* written in those times (compendia of theology, philosophy, logic, or canon law). Especially by “*Summa Theologica*” of St. Thomas Aquinas, written between 1265 and 1274, the most famous of all such compendia (De Wulf, 1956). The concept of such synthesis is well illustrated by epic poem “Divine Comedy” written in the beginning of fourteenth century by Dante Alighieri, one of the most recognized Italian poets of pre-modern times (De Wulf, 1953). The cathedrals are another example of such comprehensive synthesis. Medieval thinkers tried to reconcile an apparent conflict between reason and faith.

The idea of such reconciliation (synthesis) is evident in Gothic cathedrals. Gothic cathedral came to express the medieval movement toward synthesis in theology and philosophy. St. Thomas Aquinas's reconstruction of Christian theology based on Aristotelian principles in the *Summa Theologica* reflected the synthesis between faith and reason. (Kretzmann, et al., 1982; De Wulf, 1953)

The contrast but, at the same time, the union between an exterior (intellect or reason) and interior (spirit or faith) in the architecture of Gothic cathedrals clearly shows this movement to synthesis between reason and faith (Pevsner, 1943).

The synthesis between faith and reason, theology and logic, religious thought and every day work is illustrated by the work of a religious official regarded as the first Gothic cathedral builder - abbot Suger of St. Denis church in early twelfth century Paris, France.

Suger was born in 1081. He was dedicated to the abbey of St. Denis at the age of ten and was appointed abbot of St. Denis in 1122 (at the age of 41). He held that position until his death in 1151. St. Denis abbey was founded in the mid-seventh century by the Frankish king Dagobert in honor of Saint Denis, the patron saint of France. The old abbey church of St. Denis had been completed in 775. By Suger's time it had long been the royal abbey of France.

Elizabeth O'Reilly writes:

Saint Denis was a patron saint of France, the missionary who first preached Christianity on the Seine, and who there had been martyred ... Each of the three royal lines that have ruled France, Merovingian, Carolingian, and Capetian, chose the abbey of St. Denis as their final resting place loading it with favors. The first milestone on the highroad of Gothic art was the famous center of the nation's life, and the initiator of the new system of building was the maker of the nation's unity, Abbot Suger. (O'Reilly, 1921, p. 56)

In about 1137, the abbey of St. Denis began to be remodeled and enlarged. Abbot Suger decided to improve and rebuilt the abbey church utilizing new architectural concepts and technics of the new Gothic style – pointed arches, ribbed vaults, flying buttresses – architectural and technical solutions that transformed dignified but gloomy and insufficiently large spaces within churches into radiant, spacious chapels with soaring arches and breathtaking beauty of stained-glass lighted interiors. In 1140, after much rebuilding, the king of France, Louis VII, ceremoniously laid the cornerstone for the new construction. In the words of

Elizabeth O'Reilly: "All France was talking of the new works at St. Denis. Never before had there been such gathering of skilled masons and sculptors, of goldsmiths and glassmakers". (O'Reilly, 1921, p. 58)

On June 11, 1144, St. Denis was dedicated and the relics of the martyred Saint Denis were installed. Describing the tremendous effect of St. Denis's Gothic transformation, Nicolaus Pevsner writes in his *chef d'oeuvre* "An Outline of European Architecture":

Rib-vaults cover the varying shapes of bays, buttresses replace the massive walls between the radiating chapels which now form a continuous wavy fringe to the ambulatory. Their side walls have disappeared entirely. The effect inside the church is one of lightness, of air circulating freely, of supple curves and energetic concentration. (Pevsner, 1943, p. 91)

Since becoming abbot of St. Denis in 1122 and until his death in 1151, Suger played an important role in political, communal, and ecclesiastical affairs of Paris. While he was abbot at St. Denis, Suger even served as a regent of the kingdom from 1147-1149 while King Louis VII was on Crusade. (O'Reilly, 1921, Grant, 1998)

It seems fitting to conclude with another quote by W. R. Lethaby:

The Gothic manner of building answered to a stage in the historical development of European mind and society, it depended on the past up to its own point and embodied the spirit of its own time: adventurous, romantic, mystical, it was the architecture of chivalry, feudalism, the Guilds and religion. The form may be described and copied but only the spirit made it a live thing. (Lethaby, 1926, p. 69)

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